

3S RECIPE - Smart Shrinkage Solutions Fostering Resilient Cities in Inner Peripheries of Europe

ZONGULDAK (TR) POLICY BRIEF #3 • LIVEABILITY

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This policy brief investigates an inventory of state interventions that are judged to be most effective in creating a sustainable urban environment and maintaining a vibrant local community in Zonguldak – a small shrinking city in north-western Turkey. Amongst many initiatives, two stand out, in particular. The first is Zonguldak’s

urban renewal programme concerned with **housing provision, city centre redevelopment, and upgrading municipal facilities** and public infrastructure. The urban renewal efforts that are underway in the city are aimed at 1) regularising squatter settlements that were being built illegally, without the obligatory permits, on public land for many decades; 2) initiating the redevelopment of these residential areas; and 3) growing the stock of new, good quality housing in the city. The second – **award-winning – smart shrinkage solution** that Zonguldak offers to many mining and seaport cities across the globe concerns **repurposing industrial and maritime heritage and converting the city’s historical legacy into a liveability asset**. The key lesson learnt in Zonguldak is that a shrinking city must **prioritise urban liveability if it is to become resilient**.

INTRODUCTION

Liveability had not been on Zonguldak’s founders’ minds, when the local village was granted a city status in 1899. The latter was rather in recognition of Zonguldak’s emergence as an industrial powerhouse of the Ottoman Empire, half a century since the beginning of commercial exploitation of Turkey’s hard coal reserves in 1848. Initially, coal administration were under control of the Ottoman Imperial Navy (Admiralty), though the pits were mainly operated by British, Belgian, Italian, German, and Russian industrialists. By the early 20th century, the Zonguldak coalfield had come to be dominated by French and Italian mining concessions, especially, by the **Societe Française d’Heraclee**, founded in 1896 (see the image of French mining founders on the right). During this period, the Ottoman Ministry of Agriculture and Commerce

around 40% of the land in Zonguldak is classified as woodland, which is state-owned and administrated by the General Directorate of Forestry. As a result, only 13% of the land across the city is privately owned.

REDEVELOPING RESIDENTIAL AREAS, UPGRADING CITY INFRASTRUCTURE, BUILDING NEW HOMES

Zonguldak's enduring association with coal as well as its coal mining present have had a **profound impact** on both the city's **functional zonation** – the pattern of land use with regard to types of economic activity – and **urban morphology**, i.e., the shape of the city, including its architecture, layout of streets, and different densities of habitation. Firstly, as the result of *Teskere-i Samiye*, **80%** of the city **hold no title deeds** (legal documents), proving that someone owns a particular property, which makes tackling squatter settlements in Zonguldak a major social and political problem yet to be fully resolved. Secondly, making an improvement to the standard of living in the city, especially, dealing with poor housing conditions is a very costly business, which cannot be carried out by local inhabitants and the municipality alone. Zonguldak is **burdened by excessive building costs**, which arise from the lack of suitable land for development due to the city's particular topographical structure and many natural and manmade urban growth boundaries. These include the seashore; the difficult precipitous terrain, consisting of steep hills up to 300 metres / 1000 ft. above the sea level; protected forests surrounding the built-up area; and ground subsidence caused by a century of coal mining.

Combined with **chronic underinvestment** into the unauthorised squatter neighbourhoods, Zonguldak's urban morphology is characterised by high population density and compact form, manifesting itself in traffic congestion, air, water, and noise pollution, rudimentary technical infrastructure, and substandard amenities and social facilities. Moreover, the city's central business district (**CBD**) is spatially squeezed into a

tiny and exceedingly overcrowded area near the port, cut in half by Akgüney Creek running towards the harbour (see the image above). Finally, although Zonguldak has a long seashore, its central section has historically been occupied by a port, originally built for warehousing and shipping coal, timber, and other bulk commodities. In the late 20th century, **the seaport was modernised for commercially successful Roll-on/roll-off (Ro-Ro)¹ trade**, which prevented

the conversion of the merchant harbour into a more person-centred quality of life environment.

Facing many of the challenges outlined above, it is rather remarkable how Zonguldak has been able to **revitalise its economy by building on its historical specialisation** in coal mining as well as **developing new, knowledge-based economic activities**. During the period 2004-2019, Zonguldak city-region **expanded by 47.7%** in real gross domestic product (GDP) terms, growing on average at 3.2% per annum (p.a.), whereas Zonguldak's GDP **per capita (p.c.) grew by 80%** from US\$ 3595 to US\$ 6461, peaking in 2014 at US\$ 8937. The city-region's top five economic growth drivers in the 21st century include: i) **finance and insurance**, which registered a 6.5% p.a. growth rate in 2004-2019; ii) **mining and quarrying**; electricity, gas, and water supply (growing at 6.3% p.a.); iii) **professional, scientific, and technical activities**; and administrative support (5.4% p.a.); iv) **arts, entertainment and recreation**; and household services (3.7% p.a.); and v) **trade, transportation and storage**; and **hotels and restaurants** (3.6% p.a.). What's more, Zonguldak's strong economic performance

over the past 15 years has enabled the province to make **sizeable gains in catching-up with the rest of Turkey**: whereas the provincial GDP p.c. in 2004 stood at just 59.7% of the national average, in 2018, it reached 77.8% – **an improvement of almost 20 percentage points** in Zonguldak's relative position vis-à-vis the nation as a whole².

Capitalising on this economic resurgence, Zonguldak has rolled out a series of **urban renewal initiatives** aimed at raising the overall standard of living of the local people. The municipality – in collaboration and with support of the provincial and central government – has prioritised better **housing provision, city centre / CBD redevelopment**, and the **modernisation of municipal facilities**, especially targeting unauthorised squatter neighbourhoods.

¹ According to Beaver (2012): 'Ro-ro' or roll on/roll off refers to a ship where vehicles drive on at one end of the car ferry, either the stern or bows, and then disembark by driving off at the other end, thus no manoeuvring is necessary as vehicles continue in the same direction, speeding loading and unloading.

² <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Gross-Domestic-Product-by-Provinces-2019-33663>

In the 1980s, following an important policy change, the central government enacted a series of **Turkish Squatter Amnesty Acts** (1984-1987) for Istanbul and other major metropolitan areas, including Zonguldak (Collins, 1991). As a result, the municipality has prepared 17 urban redevelopment plans aimed at regularising uncontrolled squatter-type urbanisation on public land by a) renovating existing dwellings; b) building new, better quality homes; and c) supplying the affected neighbourhoods with basic amenities and sufficient social and technical infrastructure (e.g., see the image of a planned footbridge renovation below). Three of these urban redevelopment plans have been implemented so far.

Spatial design and architectural site planning work has also begun across the seaport, with the local authority and a number of public and private sector stakeholders collaborating to **re-envision the harbour as a major public amenity** for leisure, entertainment, recreation, and tourism. One of Zonguldak's historical landmarks – **Chargement Rapide** – a fast loading coal bridge, which inaugurated the beginnings of Zonguldak coal exporting activities in 1848, is to be redeveloped into a popular leisure facility (see the images below). Similar redevelopments around the harbour are entering the implementation phase, further enhancing the cultural and tourist offer in the city centre.

Zonguldak harbour's redevelopment: Chargement Rapide (Fast Loading) Coal Bridge - from the distant past (top left image, late 1800s) through the present time (top right image, 2017) and into the not-so-distant future (bottom images).

At the same time, with rising incomes in Zonguldak, its **growing demand for housing** has also been picked up by the **private sector**, with major national real estate developers entering the local market. During the period 2002-2019, according to Zonguldak provincial building permit statistics, **7486 new constructions** were legally started in the city-region (that is, 416 new building start-ups p.a. on average), of which, **5950 (79%)** had been **completed**, ready for occupancy. The number of **flats (apartments)** being built in new buildings in Zonguldak province during the period amounts to **61,159** (i.e., **3398 p.a. on average**), and the number of **completed flats**, ready for occupancy, had reached **42,341** (2352 p.a.). In terms of these new homes' area size, at least **12,314,818 m² (132,555,598 Sq Ft)** of new housing were initiated during this period, of which, **8,513,512 m² (91,638,680 Sq Ft)** had already been completed, ready for occupancy. To sum up, over the latest 18-year period, **13.84 m² (149 Sq Ft) of newly-completed housing stock per inhabitant** had been added in Zonguldak province as a whole, and more dwelling units are in the pipeline (see figures below)³.

In addition to the market-financed housing provision, since 2004, Zonguldak province has also been a recipient of **7 social and subsidised affordable housing developments** by Turkey's state-funded *Mass Housing Development Administration (Toplu Konut İdaresi Başkanlığı or TOKİ)*, including Zonguldak Çaycuma (under construction), Zonguldak Devrek Dağdeğirmeni (**completed**), Zonguldak Gökçebey (**completed**), Zonguldak Gökçebey Bakacakadı (**completed**), Zonguldak TTK Lojmanları (under construction), Zonguldak-Devrek-Çaydeğirmeni (under construction), and Zonguldak-Gökçebey (under construction)⁴.

As an example, **Zonguldak TTK Lojmanları** (TTK Lodgings) is a social housing project for the workers of Zonguldak's central colliery (TTK Üzülmöz), with the initial provision of 766 dwelling units and 4 shopping centres in total⁵. In September 2020, just over one-third (269 units) of these newly-built 1- to 3-bedroom flats were offered for sale to lower-middle income applicants. The terms and conditions included several subsidised 10, 13, and 15-year fixed mortgage deals, ranging from TRY 110,684 / **US\$ 14,523 for a 1-bedroom flat**⁶ of 47.6 m² (512 Sq Ft) to TRY 352,822 / **US\$ 46,294 for a 3-bedroom flat** of 119.32 m² (1284 Sq Ft)⁷.

³ <https://biruni.tuik.gov.tr/ilgosterge/?locale=tr>

⁴ <http://www.toki.gov.tr/proje-gorselleri>

⁵ <http://www.toki.gov.tr/proje-gorselleri/Zonguldak%20TTK%20Lojmanlar%C4%B1>

⁶ 1 TRY = 0.13121 USD foreign currency exchange rate for 24 Sept 2020 is used here, as per the sale applications' draw date.

⁷ <http://www.toki.gov.tr/satis/tr/duyuru-detay/zonguldak-merkez-uzulmez-ttk-lojmanlari-1-etap-766-adet-konut-4-adet-ticaret-merkezi-183489696-200823034803581/SalesAnnouncement>

REPURPOSING ZONGULDAK'S INDUSTRIAL HERITAGE

By the late 2010s, the gaze of local planners, politicians, and regional decision-makers in Turkey's Western Black Sea Region had turned to Zonguldak's outlying neighbourhoods, further away from the CBD, the harbour, and coastal area regeneration. Amongst many facets of coal mining heritage, a new **Zonguldak Tourism Development Plan** has identified a 110-year old brownfield site in Asma district, next to the functioning **TTK Üzülmöz** colliery⁸. This site, containing a derelict *lavuar* (from French *lavoire*) – coal-washing facility used to treat raw coal from Üzülmöz colliery, has become a key asset in the strategy of **improving the bad image of Zonguldak**. In 2018, **Zonguldak Governorship** (provincial administration) has agreed to help changing the public perception of the city from dirty, polluted, mining town towards a much more liveable city with attractive entertainment, arts, culture, and leisure facilities by funding the regeneration of the old Üzülmöz lavuar site. The **Üzülmöz Culture Valley** project was later included in the central government-supported *Zonguldak Nature and Culture Tourism* (Project 67) development programme. According to the project's creators – **Kivi Stratejik Planlama AŞ** [Kiwi Strategic Planning Inc.] and **BUDA Mimarlık** [BUDA Architecture Design] – Üzülmöz Culture Valley should be all about “accepting the coal production process as a culturally wealthy piece of memory to be preserved”⁹. By locating this project on a “contextually cultural memory ground,” its instigators plan to restore and repurpose the coal-washery for arts and culture, thus, contributing to the enrichment of urban living and historical memories of Zonguldak¹⁰.

Üzülmöz TTK Lavuar Coal-Washery¹¹ is located around 3.7 km (2.2 miles) from the harbour on the Zonguldak-Ankara motorway (State road D.750). The brownfield site consists of a number of abandoned buildings and structures, most notably, the masonry building of 1907 (the *Lavuar* itself; see the image above by [Railway News, 2020](#)) and a reinforced concrete M-shaped roof workshops building with annexes completed in 1936. Both buildings are listed in Turkey's **Industrial Cultural Heritage Inventory**. During the project, the site will be cleared of redundant auxiliary buildings and

⁸ <http://taskomuru.net/tr/uzulmez-t-i-m/>

⁹ <https://www.budamim.com/kopyasi-can>

¹⁰ Watch a 51-minute conversation about the project with Burak Pelenk of BUDA Mimarlık (in Turkish) here: <https://youtu.be/DAR4mCDv8pg>

¹¹ Address: Ladin Sokak 12-30, Asma, 67040 Zonguldak, Turkey.

structures, whilst its two main buildings will be refurbished and repurposed, with minimum intervention, and with the authentic architectural elements being preserved¹².

As the main outcome, the Üzülmöz Culture Valley project will establish a new cultural campus as a place i) to **celebrate** these **industrial structures** as a **significant symbol** in the social and economic memory of the city; ii) to draw attention to Zonguldak's industrial history and the **visually important characteristics of an epoch gone by**; and iii) to **integrate** this part of the city by **re-functioning** it in line with the **current spatial needs**, including modern public social spaces, arts studios, and culture halls (see the images above and below by Kivi Stratejik Planlama¹³ and BUDA Mimarlık¹⁴). In particular, the TTK Lavuar building is to be transformed into **Zonguldak Geo Park Visitor Centre** – an exhibition gallery of natural and industrial history models, photographs, objects, and artefacts. In turn, the workshops building will become

Üzülmöz Culture Ateliers – an artistic space for representing all traces of the past to the present, and using coal and coal-washing as a main reflection point. The two venues will be story-telling the history of the city and, at the same time, serving as a multi-purpose sociocultural activity area.

¹² <https://www.kivi.com.tr/2019/02/13/zonguldak-uzulmez-kultur-vadisi/>

¹³ <https://www.kivi.com.tr/2019/02/13/zonguldak-uzulmez-kultur-vadisi/>

¹⁴ <https://www.budamim.com/kopyasi-can>

Eventually, Üzülmöz Culture Valley will expand into an open exhibition space, equipped with industrial objects such as machines, hand tools, rail lines, coal transport carts, reminding the visitors about the centuries-old coal mining traditions and practices. To this end, the project will include the construction of an **immersive experience tunnel** into the renovated No. 63 **Derebaca colliery**, which will become a museum. The project has utilised only **locally-sourced** and **symbolic building materials** such as Zonguldak's **basalt stone**, **crushed-coarse river sand**, **natural stone**, **rusted steel** (for railings, display element supports, water beams, wall coverings, structural landscape lines), and **hard coal**, which is to be laid in heaps in designated areas.

DELIVERING ÜZÜLMEZ CULTURE VALLEY: PRACTICAL MECHANISMS

Following the project's approval by the Turkish Ministry of Industry and Technology, on **15th May 2020**, Zonguldak provincial government signed the contract for the delivery of Üzülmöz Culture Valley **within 24 months** with the Western Black Sea Regional Development Agency (BAKKA), the Municipality of Zonguldak, Zonguldak Provincial Culture and Tourism Directorate, TTK, and the relevant sub-contractual parties. The project's **construction area covers 2850 m² (30,680 Sq Ft)**, whilst its **total land area** extends to 10,670 m² (**106.7 ha / 264 acres**). The **total budget** of the

project is set at TRY 19,715,016 / **US\$ 2,856,706¹⁵**. Üzülmöz Culture Valley has become a true symbol of Zonguldak's regeneration. On 18th September 2020, **Eda Yazkurt Pelenk** and **Burak Pelenk** – the project's main architects of BUDA Mimarlık – won Turkey's most prestigious **Chamber of Architects' 17th National Architecture Award¹⁶**.

To identify the practical mechanisms, driving this project's celebrated success, we have used a distinctive in-house *Urban Futures* methodology designed to facilitate stakeholders' collective reflection and learning about a particular solution, its benefits, and the necessary conditions for effective urban regeneration (Lombardi *et al*, 2012). During a special workshop on 22nd February 2019, hosted by the Mayor and Municipality of Zonguldak, the local stakeholders and smart shrinkage practitioners debated the city's urban renewal efforts. First of all, they underlined the importance of the public land squatter amnesty, leading to regularisation of the existing settlements, and redevelopment of neighbourhoods threatened by ground subsidence. Furthermore, increasing the housing supply with high quality homes, which are made affordable to lower income residents, was defined as yet another essential policy to reverse urban shrinkage. With regard to Üzülmöz Cultural Valley, local stakeholders were able to identify two main intended

¹⁵ <https://www.bakka.gov.tr/haber/uzulmez-kultur-vadisi-gudumlu-proje-destegi-sozlesmesi-imzalandi/1102>

¹⁶ <http://www.naturadergi.com/anasayfa/2020-ulusal-mimarlik-odulleri-sahiplerini-buldu/?lang=en>

sustainability benefits such as: 1) the **production of social space dedicated to modern arts and culture**; this should tackle the current city-wide shortage of high-quality event facilities and make a tangible improvement in the standard of living of local residents; and (2) a **marked increase in liveability and attractiveness** of the city-region to visitors; this would contribute to economic sustainability of Zonguldak and enhance its tourism potential. Moreover, the local actors involved in the Üzülmöz Culture Valley project highlighted **four specific enabling conditions** to make it happen, as follows:

Outcome	What are the necessary conditions that make it happen?
1. New outstanding space for arts and cultural activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional: co-ordination between the central and local governments, in addition to collaborative work between relevant public sector institutions and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) is vital. • Financial: allocation of adequate financial resources by the central government as the initiator of the project is extremely important to complete the project promptly and on time. • Architecture and design: high quality architectural design of the project, including attractive features that are suitable for local users as well as outside visitors is key to its long-term success. • Project management: timely project delivery and good management of the area of intervention, generating a safe public environment with high-quality leisure and recreational facilities that are attractive the local community, families with children, young adults, and tourists.
2. Marked increase in urban liveability and attractiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional: co-ordination between the central and local governments, in addition to collaborative work between relevant public sector institutions and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) is vital. • Financial: allocation of adequate financial resources by the central government as the initiator of the project is extremely important to complete the project promptly and on time. • Architecture and design: high quality architectural design of the project, including attractive features that are suitable for local users as well as outside visitors is key to its long-term success. • Project management: timely project delivery and good management of the area of intervention, generating a safe public environment with high-quality leisure and recreational facilities that are attractive the local community, families with children, young adults, and tourists.

RECOMMENDATIONS: LEARNING FROM THE ÜZÜLMÖZ CULTURE VALLEY PROJECT

➤ **Urban liveability is of utmost importance to make a shrinking city resilient**

For many families, urban liveability is a determining factor in their decision to stay or to leave a city. What has clearly become apparent from many conversations held with the local and regional stakeholders is that urban liveability is also a determining factor in personal decisions to start a business, that is, urban liveability fosters entrepreneurial ambition.

➤ **Housing quality is a vital driver of liveability, community-building, and social cohesion**

This is particularly significant for the local communities located in areas affected by subsidence. Many local residents in neighbourhoods threatened by subsidence feel neglected and excluded from city life. They require a more pro-active government response orientated towards improving housing quality, providing municipal infrastructure, whilst maintaining affordability.

➤ **Arts and culture and spaces that can attract artistic activities and host cultural events are of great value in radically improving the image of a shrinking city**

Usually, people living in an old industrial shrinking city feel depressed, although they are strongly attached to the city, and enjoy strong social networks. What they really want is to change the image of their city as a grim and grubby mining town caught in a spiral of decline. Arts, culture, festivals, and attractive events can be useful in improving public perceptions of a city.

WOULD REPURPOSED INDUSTRIAL HERITAGE DELIVER THE SAME BENEFITS WHATEVER THE FUTURE BRINGS?

During this project, we have tested whether the smart shrinking solutions proposed in the context of creating a liveable city will deliver their intended benefits over a 40-year regeneration cycle. In particular, we have appraised the likely future performance of each urban regeneration-related ‘smart shrinkage solution-benefit pair’ – that is, actions taken today in the name of sustainable urban development – in a series of possible future scenarios for the year 2060. If a proposed solution delivers a positive legacy regardless of the future against which it is tested, then it can be adopted with confidence. Four **plausible but distinct** future scenarios were included into our analysis (see Lombardi et. al., 2012: Table 2). A summary of these four global **urban future scenarios** is provided below:

New Sustainability Paradigm (NSP)		Key driver: Equity and sustainability
Settlement pattern 	Description An ethos of 'one planet living' facilitates a shared vision for more sustainable living and a much improved quality of life. New socio-economic arrangements result in changes to the character of urban industrial civilisation. Local is valued but global links also play a role. A sustainable and more equitable future is emerging from new values, a revised model of development and the active engagement of civil society.	Philosophy The worldview of the <i>New Sustainability Paradigm</i> has few historical precedents, although John Stuart Mill, the nineteenth century political economist, was prescient in theorising a post-industrial and post-scarcity social arrangement based on human development rather than material acquisition (Mill, 1848).
Policy Reform (PR)		Key driver: Economic growth with greater equity
Settlement pattern 	Description <i>Policy Reform</i> depends on comprehensive and coordinated government action for poverty reduction and environmental sustainability, negating trends toward high inequity. The values of consumerism and individualism persist, creating a tension with policies that prioritise sustainability.	Philosophy In <i>Policy Reform</i> , the belief is that markets require strong policy guidance to address inherent tendencies toward economic crisis, social conflict and environmental degradation. John Maynard Keynes, influenced by the Great Depression, is an important predecessor of those who hold that it is necessary to manage capitalism in order to temper its crises (Keynes, 1936).
Market Forces (MF)		Key driver: Competitive, open global markets
Settlement pattern 	Description <i>Market Forces</i> relies on the self-correcting logic of competitive markets. Current demographic, economic, environmental, and technological trends unfold without major surprise. Competitive, open and integrated markets drive world development. Social and environmental concerns are secondary.	Philosophy The <i>Market Forces</i> bias is one of market optimism, the faith that the hidden hand of well-functioning markets is the key to resolving social, economic and environmental problems. An important philosophic antecedent is Adam Smith (1776), while contemporary representatives include many neo-classical economists and free market enthusiasts.
Fortress World (FW)		Key driver: Protection and control of resources
Settlement pattern 	Description Powerful individuals, groups and organisations develop an authoritarian response to the threats of resource scarcity and social breakdown by forming alliances to protect their own interests. Security and defensibility of resources are paramount for these privileged rich elites. An impoverished majority exists outside the fortress. Policy and regulation exist but enforcement may be limited. Armed forces act to impose order, protect the environment and prevent a societal collapse.	Philosophy The <i>Fortress World</i> mindset was foreshadowed by the philosophy of Thomas Hobbes (1651), who held a pessimistic view of the nature of man and saw the need for powerful leadership. While it is rare to find modern Hobbesians, many people believe, in their resignation and anguish, that some kind of a <i>Fortress World</i> is the logical outcome of the unattended social polarisation and environmental degradation they observe.

The **Urban Future Method** (Lombardi et. al., 2012) applied here does not favour any particular scenario. Indeed, for a solution to be determined to be robust and resilient to future change, the necessary conditions to support the intended benefits being achieved over time must exist in all scenarios. Drawing on expertise, experience, and **knowledge of the local context**, we have graded the likely performance of the Üzülmöz Cultural Valley project in the future as follows:

Urban Futures Method applied to Üzülmez Cultural Valley				
Necessary Conditions	New Sustainability Paradigm	Policy Reform	Market Forces	Fortress World
Institutional co-ordination between central and local governments, and collaborative work between relevant public sector institutions and NGOs	Collaborative work, co-production, and co-ordination of sustainable urban development initiatives aimed at repurposing industrial heritage is part of the everyday toolbox of participatory planning and active community engagement	The importance of co-ordination between different central government bodies is recognised in policies. However, central government actors still dominate new urban development and regeneration projects and could override local concerns and ignore local voices	High deregulation of planning policy hinders government co-ordination attempts. Market drivers dominate new urban development and regeneration projects, side-lining public bodies and local communities	The fortress world is highly fragmented and segregated to allow for cross-boundary collaboration. The rich will protect access to arts and cultural facilities for private use. The poor have no voice in decision-making
Adequate public funding by the central government	Post-industrial rehabilitation is highly valued, with local community engagement ensuring cost-effective use of public funds. However, small local authorities and individual volunteers have to rely on external financial backing even for a medium-scale project, potentially competing with numerous other sustainable urban development initiatives	Long-term investment into urban infrastructure and services is publicly funded and supported by policy to boost demand, accelerate economic growth, and help maintain party-political support	Public infrastructure investment is limited due to strong budgetary constraints. Almost no public investment is made available to small peripheral cities. Market forces may play an active role in urban regeneration based on re-use of industrial heritage, if the private sector considers such projects commercially viable	All investment is poured into prime 'winner' locations and sucked out of struggling urban areas. The rich have no interest in celebrating industrial heritage and the working-class history. Poor communities chronically lack even the most basic of local amenities. None are provided by the state
High quality architectural design with attractive features for different user groups	Building standards and construction practices conform to high spatial and ecological design requirements. Locally sourced materials are prioritised	Redevelopments are driven to enhance the urban quality of life and retain residents. However, municipal planning policies force the issue of generic, basic standard provision, with people having to choose whether to use them. Only some community needs for arts and culture amenities are met	There is no policy enforcing or supporting the promotion of better spatial and ecological design and/or higher environmental standards. Market may demand it, nonetheless, for commercially attractive developments	Strong enforcement of policy that supports better design and higher environmental standards for the rich. For the poor, many buildings and spaces are very run-down and unsafe, due to poor design and lack of maintenance
Timely project delivery and good management of the area of intervention	Local community members effectively manage and maintain public spaces, buildings, and shared facilities. However, smaller communities may lack sufficient municipal resources even for a medium-scale investment and have to rely on central government grants, and on charitable donations and voluntary contributions from the outside to deliver such projects. This could lead to frequent delays in the project's completion.	Existence of planning policies to ensure management and maintenance of open public spaces and shared facilities. Yet a state interventionist approach may suffer from frequent discontinuities and serious changes in government direction, leading to intermittent funding and a high degree of turnover of senior management	Private-led management is based on willingness to pay, hence, a modern arts gallery or high-end museum might be well maintained, depending on the fee-paying strength of its customer base	The rich support management and maintenance of their spaces and buildings; for the poor, many buildings and spaces are unsafe due to poor design and limited/no resources for management and maintenance

Key: ■ condition highly unlikely to continue in the future ■ condition is at risk in the future ■ condition highly likely to continue in the future

POLICY IMPLICATIONS

Upgrading urban infrastructure, redeveloping run-down neighbourhoods, tackling poor housing, and repurposing industrial heritage for the needs and wants of modern society could become the **most effective package of measures** to reverse a decline in a city's fortunes. Particularly, these interventions are of greatest value in regenerating a shrinking, old industrial city – the one that suffers from chronic underinvestment, bad publicity, and a noticeable lack of stylish amenities for younger adults and the trendy middle classes. The research findings reported above show that projects aimed at turning the old industrial legacy of a shrinking city into a valuable asset for the new creative economy have the highest chance of long-term success in the **New Sustainability Paradigm** urban future scenario, with **75% of the necessary conditions** that ensure such a project's resilience being present. The **Policy Reform** urban future scenario offers a **62.5% chance of success**, due to the availability of generous central government funding for public infrastructure. In the **Market Forces** urban future scenario, an initiative aimed at repurposing a shrinking city's industrial heritage would have a **50/50** chance of success. Finally, the odds are stacked against a project like this succeeding in the **Fortress World** urban future, with just 1/4 of the necessary conditions being present.

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